

Microfinance, Poverty Reduction and Economy Activity

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Abstract

This paper examines the role of microfinance in poverty reduction and employment generation in different part of Nepal and tries to make significant contribution in the area of financial sectors and poverty. This paper investigates how microfinance strategy of financial institutions helps to reduce poverty through employment generation. The questionnaires survey results suggested that the package of microfinance for small scale enterprises of financial system in the Nepal has a positive impact in economy activity, i.e. it helps to reduce poverty. Poverty of Nepal can be reduced by accelerating microfinance for small scale enterprises.

KEYWORDS: Microfinance system, Poverty, Economic Growth and Business Enterprise

BACKGROUND

Nepal is among the poorest least developed countries in the world with nearly 31 percent of its population living below the poverty line. Agriculture is the mainstay of the economy, providing a livelihood for over 80 percent of the population and accounting for 41 percent of GDP, Economic Survey (2013).

In this paper presents what roles of microfinance perform in economy activity. According to various theoretical literatures about finance and economic growth are based on the role of microfinance for poverty reduction in the economy. How development of financial system helps reduce poverty are clearly related issues because growth is a powerful way to reduce poverty Bruno, Ravallion, and Squire (1998). As Kanbur (2001) emphasized, though there have been many demonstrations that across countries and over time growth in real national per capita

income is correlated with reductions in the measure of national income poverty. The development of financial system helps reduce poverty indirectly by stimulating growth and directly by facilitating transactions and allowing the poor to benefit from financial services (primarily savings products) that increase their income (through interest earned) and enhance their ability to undertake profitable investments and other activities Bhandari (2012). Poverty of Nepal can be reduced by accelerating microfinance activity. The microfinance activity will trickle down to the poor in the form of more employment opportunities, greater productivity and higher wages.

The government of Nepal has a fundamental economic responsibility to create an independent and self-reliant economy through equitable distribution

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of economic resources and gains, prevention of economic exploitation, and the advancement of private and public enterprise. However, according to observers, such changes require economic reforms that have yet to materialize. Prior to 1990, the economy, like the country, was essentially closed to the world, and international economic relations were largely in the form of cross-border trade with India and China. Since 1990, the government increasingly has adopted market-oriented policies with greater liberalization of the domestic economy and trade. These policies have focused on privatizing state industries and creating joint-venture projects, particularly in financial institutions. Liberalization policies, however, have been criticized for benefiting primarily urban areas and rural elites. The economy is still characterized by central planning. Indeed, the government is the main source of domestic investment, and five-year plans direct such investment (Economic Survey, 2012). However, five-year economic development plans alternately emphasize various sectors, and as a result, development has been uneven (NRB, 2012).

The economy has been and continues to be characterized by dependence on agricultural output, a poor export base but strong reliance on trade, unbalanced regional development, dependence on foreign aid, excessive government control and regulation, and inefficient public enterprises and administration (Economic Survey, 2007). The agricultural sector has employed most of the labor force and provided the largest share of gross domestic product (GDP), but the sector's shares of the labor force and GDP have declined since the 1970s. Industry and manufacturing have provided lower portions of GDP, employed fewer people, and expanded little. Services, particularly those related to tourism, have grown in importance, but the civil conflict has hurt this and other sectors (NSA, 1998).

The proper mobilization and utilization of domestic resources is one of the key factors in the economic development of a country. Similarly, integrated and speedy development of the country is only possible when competitive and reliable financial institution services are reached and operated to every corner of

the country. Financial institutions have vital roles in the process of economic development. Financial performance, especially microfinance institutions has long term impact not only on their growth and sustainability but also on the economic development of the country. (The World Bank; 1966:232)

Financial market, financial intermediaries and financial management are crucial elements of well developed financial system. In Nepal rural development bank, cooperatives banks, international non-government organization and donor institutions, ADB/N, UNDP, International Funds for Agriculture Development through NGOs, Local Government aid, Government of Nepal are rendering micro finance services. In addition, informal institution such as Dhukuti association, user groups, indigenous bankers and businessmen are providing microfinance services to low income household, poor and micro enterprise.

Microfinance helps to enhance economic activities thereby increase in income, self employment and livelihood of the poor people. Microfinance has been one of the few effective tools for poverty reduction over the past years. Through the creation of sound microfinance institutions and systems, poor people can safely deposit money and accumulate funds for future investments or emergencies as well as access loans for productive purposes leading to higher incomes. The poor rarely access services through the formal financial sector. They address their need for financial services through a variety of financial relationships, mostly informal. They participate in informal savings groups where everyone contributes a small amount of cash each day, week, or month, and is successively awarded the pot on a rotating basis. Some of these groups allow members to borrow from the pot as well. The poor also give their money to neighbors to hold or pay local cash collectors to keep it safe.

In the least developed country like Nepal, Micro finance is an important and powerful tool for gradual reduction of poverty and it is must to uplift the poor women and to make them independent and make them feel they can also do something for their family and the community besides their

household work. Micro finance enables poor and encourages them to take advantages of the existing opportunities by providing them affordable and appropriate financial services. It helps to generate self employment, develops micro enterprises, and raises income level, builds up self confidence, empowers women and provides opportunities to the poor, under privilege caste and inequality. The clients of microfinance are typically self employed and household based entrepreneurs.

Micro finance can help poor people to increase income, build viable business. It can also be powerful instrument for self empowerment by enabling the poor, especially women to become economic agent of change. We have found micro finance program very effective in creating self employment and poverty alleviation. But only few areas are covered by the financial institutions providing such services.

Economic liberalization policy of the government has encouraged the establishment and growth of the financial institutions in the country. With the growing number of financial institutions, the target group will be benefited from such institutions. The major objective of the all microfinance programs is to enhance the deprived groups socially and economically. Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank is also proving microfinance services in various cities of some districts. This research study will concern on how microfinance program of Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank support in creation of micro enterprises and employment. General objective of this research is to analyze the micro finance program on members under Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank. The specific objectives are; the role of microfinance in employment generation through micro enterprises and examine the social status improvement of the women after joining the microfinance program.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The history of modern financial system of Nepal was begun in 1937 with the establishment of the Nepal Bank Ltd. (NBL) as the first commercial bank of Nepal with the joint ownership of government and general public (Shrestha and Bhandari, 2007). However, the activities of the bank was confined

to accepting deposits & providing loans only to the commercial sector in Kathmandu and other limited urban areas. Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB), the central bank of Nepal, was established in 1956 with the central banking responsibilities of guiding the development of the embryonic domestic financial sector (Bhandari, 2012). After the establishment of NRB, Nepal witnessed a systematic development of the financial system. In the initial years of operation the NRB had been focusing towards monetization of the economy by circulating Nepalese currency all over the country. After achieving some progress it started taking initiation towards institutional development. Consequently, Nepal Industrial Development Bank, Employee's Provident Fund (EPF), Cooperative Bank, National Insurance Corporation, Agricultural Development Bank (ADB/N) and Rastriya Banijya Bank (RBB) have been established (Shrestha and Bhandari, 2008).

Table 1: Financial Institutional Development from 1956 to 1980

Year	Institutions
1937	Nepal Bank Ltd.
1956	Nepal Rastra Bank [Centre Bank of Nepal]
1957	Nepal Industrial Development Bank
1962	Employee's Provident Fund (EPF)
1963	Cooperative Bank [merged with ADB/N in 1968]
1966	Rastriya Banijya Bank
1967	National Insurance Corporation
1968	Agriculture Development Bank
1968	Land Reform Savings Corporation
1968	National Insurance Corporation
1974	Credit Guarantee Corporation
1975	Agriculture Project Services Centre
1977	Securities Market Centre (converted in to SEC in 1984 and into NEPSE in 1992)
1977	Postal Saving Offices

Source: *Economic Survey (1996, 2000, 2005) and Nepal Rastra Bank (2006, 2007)*

Nepal has given high priority to alleviate poverty through planned efforts. Policies and programs have been initiated for improving the standard of living of the people, and reducing the gap between rich and poor. Mitigating poverty problem has, thus, become a major challenge. One way to increase the productivity of the poor is through broad-based economic growth. Such growth ensures more inclusive participation in development by providing widespread employment opportunities.

According to Mohammad Yunus, founder of Grameen Bank, women have plans for themselves, for their children, for their home. They have a vision. Men want to enjoy themselves. Many supporters from women's organization worldwide have charged micro credit or microfinance organization with the responsibility of affecting change at the grassroots level. Since women represent a majority of the poorest of the poor, such programs have already targeted them. Economic empowerment has been shown to occur in most micro finance program as the most natural result of micro finance, Yunus (2003).

The Grameen Bank and other financial institutions especially targeted their loan to the female clients. Economic empowerment has been measured in terms of

- Women have control over the loan profits and savings.
- Flexibility on decision making on financial matters especially expenditure and assets creation.
- Family assistance in enterprise
- Taking Product to market and
- Doing most of the accounting themselves.

The study based on Bangladesh found that women participating in micro finance program had higher degree of economic empowerment than the control group of women with no loans (Hashemi 1996). The microfinance focus banks pioneer of micro finance programs in south Asia is also known for being

catalyst for social change in Bangladesh. It has added features to its simple groups lending model that have led to change in the social and political lives of women, Yunus (2003).

Certain components of the microfinance programs have served to help it work toward these goals. The "Sixteen Decision" of Grameen Bank has tried to expose women to ideas about nutrition and childcare. In addition the Grameen Bank encourages women who have been repeated borrowers, to take out loans for their homes. One caveat to this program is that women must put the property title in their own names and not their husband. Over 400000 men agreed to allow their wives hold the title to their home because housing is so scarce in Bangladesh. This enables woman to have more control over her life and can increase her life and can increase her status in the eyes of her husband (UNIFEM). The Nepali study found that over half of the women participants felt that their families treated them with more respect than before they had joined the programs. An additional 40 percent felt that they were respected as equal as their husband by their families, Sharma and Upreti (2003). Therefore all of these targeted programs focus on poverty alleviation and the enhancement of women's social and economic status.

Microfinance, thus, gives the unemployed and the poor some opportunities, hope and self-esteem. Being employed (whether self-employed or by an employer) gives a person a significant boost to his/her sense of self-respect and dignity. Furthermore, microcredit allows people to signal their creditworthiness. If their success makes banks more willing to lend them larger sums and leads to even more economic activity, then that should help reduce poverty in the long run, Chowdhury (2009).

Poverty reduction is an overarching objective of targeted microfinance programs. Because poor people with little education and land more likely to participate in microfinance programs than are other groups, impact assessments of micro-finance and poverty reduction should assess whether program participation increases household consumption over its level before program participation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the way to systematically solve the research problem. It includes the various steps that are adopted by the researcher to solve the problem along with the logic behind them. In this study, descriptive and analytical research design has been adopted. Descriptive approach has been used mainly for conceptualization of the problem and analytical approach has been used to analyze and interpret the quantitative and qualitative data collected from the concerned field.

Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank Limited (DLB Bank) is promoted with the equity participation of Nabil Bank Ltd, Nepal Bank Ltd, Agriculture Development Bank Ltd, Lumbini Finance and Leasing Company Ltd, Development Project Service Center (NGO), CEAPRED (NGO) and former bankers. The main objective of the bank is to provide competent and sustainable microfinance services and to empower the woman from backward communities. The bank is working in 25 districts with the approval of Nepal Rastra Bank. Bank has 79658 members and 58305 clients in different part of Nepal. Out of total population 79658 members and 58305 clients, 230 members are randomly selected in this study as sample size.

Data required to conduct this research study is basically obtained from primary source conducting field survey, direct interview and observation. However, secondary source of information is also used to some relevant areas by reviewing official documents, periodic and annual progress reports of Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank and other related literature.

Individual microfinance client, frontline field supervisor and microfinance group, were the primary source of information. Besides key local level stakeholder, Branch Manager, and Branch Office of Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank have remained the primary source of information in the process of preparing key institutional issues, program policy issues and their perception. Data also has been collected through questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the process of fulfilling objectives of the research, collected data are tabulated and presented followed by analysis and interpretation in this section. As mentioned in the research methodology the data are presented and analyzed in accordance with the sequential of questionnaires; the role of microfinance in poverty reduction and employment generation and improvement in economic status of the clients.

One of the most important objectives of this study has to find out the role of microfinance program in creation of enterprise and employment generation. According to the field survey purpose of loan taking of the respondents has to start a small scale business. Micro finance program of Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank has seemed helpful for poorest people to start their own micro enterprises. Data presented below shows the loan taking purpose, its objective utilization and business creation with employment generation.

Table 2 shows the mentioned purpose of taking loan from the micro-finance institution. Maximum number of respondent 196 (85.21%) was taking loan for the purpose of micro level business. Very little 28 (12.17%) respondents were taking loan for domestic use, which is not the productive work. This purpose has not mentioned with the bank while taking loan. Only 6 (2.6%) respondents were taking for the repayment of old due loan. In this way different person takes loan for the fulfillment of his or her own needs and wants.

Table 2: Purpose of Taking Loan

SN	Main purpose of taking loan	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Domestic use	28	12
2	Investment in business	196	85
3	Repayment of old loan	6	3
Total		230	100%

Source: Field Survey 2013.

In Table 2 it is presented that 196 (85.21%) respondents are using loan for specified purpose to start their business whereas 19(16.53%) respondents loan is not using in specified purpose and we found that they are using their funds for their personal needs.

In Table 3; it is presented data from field survey shows that out of 230 respondents, 186 respondents have established different kinds of business, which indicates business start up percentage is 80.86, and remaining 44 (19.14%) respondents have not started any business.

Table 3: Establishment of Business

Sector wise Enterprises	No. of Enterprise Created	Percentage
Agriculture	12	6.45
Livestock	34	18.27
Manufacturing enterprises	8	4.3
Trade business	114	61.29
Service business	18	9.67
Total	186	100

Sources: Field Survey: 2013

As above table presented nearly 6 percent members are started agriculture firms such as vegetable farming, fruits, and other cash crops. Livestock such as cows, buffalos, poultry, goat and pig rising is equal to 34(18%) and manufacturing enterprises such as diary, furniture, food processing are 8 (4%). Similarly services such as transports services, beauty parlor, barber, photo studio and tailoring are 18(9%). The maximum number 57 (62%) of respondent are involving trading business.

The main objective of this study is to investigate the roles of microfinance program on employment generation and poverty reduction. Small scale enterprises are the main sources of self employment generation for the poor people. In Table 4, data show that from 50 different enterprises, 278 persons have been getting full employment. Maximum number 154(55.4%) of employment has generated from the trade and business which includes hotel, grocery, cosmetic etc and only few i.e. 24 (8.63%)

employment from agro based enterprise has been generated.

Table 4: Employment Generation Details

SN	Sector wise Enterprise	Total number of full employment	%
1	Agriculture	24	8.63
2	Livestock	34	12.23
3	Manufacturing enterprises	30	10.79
4	Trade business	154	55.4
5	Service business	36	12.95
Total		278	

Source: Field survey 2013.

In Table 5 presented the sources of income after joining microfinance program. It shows currents with the discussion of sampled respondents, we found that the level of income has shifted. Sale of live stocks' products were the main source of income before joining the program but after joining the microfinance program the survey shows that the sources of income has the small scale business and the sale of agricultural products and livestock. The pattern of income sources describe after joining to the microfinance program.

Table 5: Sources of Income

SN	Sources of income	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1	Agriculture	32	13.91
2	Livestock	46	20
3	Manufacturing enterprises	24	10.43
4	Trade business	122	53.04
5	Other	6	2.6
Total		230	100

Source: Field Survey 2013.

From the Table 5, out of 230 sampled respondents, 32 (14%) respondents' major source of income is based on agriculture, 46 (20%) respondents' source

of income is livestock, 24(10.43%) respondents' sources of income is manufacturing enterprises and a large number of respondents 122 (53.04%) respondents' source of income is trade business. The data show that very low number of respondent's i.e.6 (3%) main income source is other sources.

The survey reveals that the micro- finance program has not shown a significant effect on the clients' landholding position. Almost all the clients have their own home to live but not sufficient land to cultivate except some vegetables. After involving in such micro financing program, there is no differences found in creating the fixed assets like landholding. Only 6 (2.6%) respondents have invested their income into land. Remaining 224 respondents said that they have not purchase any land and building. This shows that the impact of microfinance doesn't show any positive movements for adding the land. The survey showed that there have been 26 respondents of their livestock holding. The survey showed that 80 (34.78%) sample respondents have invested their income for business expansion after joining the microfinance. In table 6 surveys showed that 118 (51.30%) respondents have no any additional investment in productive sectors. They have utilized their income in child education, clothing, house rent, medicine and other miscellaneous expenses.

Table 6: Investment Status

SN	Sectors of Investment	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1	Land & building	6	2.6
2	Livestock purchase	26	11.30
3	Business expansion	80	34.78
4	Domestic use only	118	51.30

Source: Field Survey 2013

One of the main objectives of this study is to identify the standard of living and poverty rate after involve the microfinance services. In additional, quality of health, income and consumption and educational standards are also can be used to measure standard of living and poverty. **Standard of living is a level of consumption that an individual, group, or nation has achieved.** The evaluation of a standard

of living is relative, depending upon the judgment of the observer. On the basis of discussion with respondents, their income level has changed because of having additional revenue from microfinance program. The general accepted principle about the expenditure is that higher the poverty and deprivation, higher is the proportion of expenditure done for food and basic amenities. If revenue increased purchasing capacity also increases. Most of the respondents have positively increased their purchasing capacity.

Living standard of the people represents living house, wearing clothing or fashion style and the food habits. During the interview time we observed and they described that they improved the quality of house by changing their roof, making ground etc. In the survey showed that sample clients have improved their life style and reduced their poverty level. Satisfactory economic impacts are not observed in assets creation such as land and building and saving amount but the microfinance services provided to them have helped them to improve their better livelihood structure. Positive social impacts are observed in their livelihood structure and have empowered women in many ways such as awareness on basic issues such as importance educating children, participation in community activities, their role in household economy etc. The significant social impacts, increased awareness, confidence and living in a more dignified life itself and somehow the improvement in economic level are remarkable achievements in the field of poverty reduction and women empowerment. This study carried out an impact assessment follow-up survey and findings on the poverty effects of microfinance program. The finding of this study is microfinance continues to reduce poverty among poor borrowers and within the local economy. It raises income level, living standard of the clients.

The program has made participating client more disciplined and conscious on time management. Awareness on enterprises handling, trading and local economic scenario have upgraded. The social interaction and community level, harmony and mutual cooperation have increased. On top of these, sample clients are very much careful in

maintaining their social dignity by repaying the loan installment in time. Probably, this is one of the main reasons that microfinance is focused towards women. However, good repayment cannot be rationalized only with discipline and pressure but also with better return from their investment which has been proven from the analysis. Despite having a number of areas to improve and strengthen, microfinance services targeted to women clients have open up lots of avenues of empowering them. In addition to providing loan and other financial facilities to women, they should also be given training to develop their skill and knowledge in micro enterprises so that they can do better to sustain economically.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper presents what roles of microfinance perform in economy activity. According to various theoretical literatures about finance and economic growth are based on the role of microfinance for poverty reduction in the economy. How development of financial system helps reduce poverty are clearly related issues because growth is a powerful way to reduce poverty and income is correlated with reductions in the measure of national income poverty. The microfinance program helps reduce poverty indirectly by stimulating growth and directly by facilitating transactions and allowing the poor to benefit from financial services (primarily savings products) that increase their income (through interest earned) and enhance their ability to undertake profitable investments and other activities. Poverty of Nepal can be reduced by accelerating microfinance activity. The microfinance activity will trickle down to the poor in the form of more employment opportunities, greater productivity and higher wages.

Microfinance helps to enhance economic activities thereby increase in income, self employment and livelihood of the poor people. It has been one of the few effective tools for poverty reduction over the past years. Through the creation of sound microfinance institutions and systems, poor people can safely deposit money and accumulate funds for future investments or emergencies as well as access

loans for productive purposes leading to higher incomes. The poor rarely access services through the formal financial sector. They address their need for financial services through a variety of financial relationships, mostly informal. They participate in informal savings groups where everyone contributes a small amount of cash each day, week, or month, and is successively awarded the pot on a rotating basis. Some of these groups allow members to borrow from the pot as well. The poor also give their money to neighbors to hold or pay local cash collectors to keep it safe. Micro finance can help poor people to increase income, build viable business. It can also be powerful instrument for self empowerment by enabling the poor, especially women to become economic agent of change. We have found micro finance program very effective in creating self employment and poverty alleviation.

Access to microfinance services offered by Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank has positive impacts on the life of surveyed sample in different part of Nepal. Micro finance program of Deprosc Laghubitta Bikas Bank has highly positive impact and vital role in enterprises creation and employment generation. It seems helpful to start enterprises. Moreover, the loans have been mostly invested on small scale business, medium and small livestock and somehow in agriculture (in growing seasonal vegetable), since participating are not capacitated with upgraded skills and knowledge for market oriented value addition in micro enterprises.

Satisfactory economic impacts are not observed in assets creation such as land and building and saving amount but the microfinance services provided to them have helped them to improve their better livelihood structure. Positive social impacts are observed in their livelihood structure and have empowered women in many ways such as awareness on basic issues such as importance of educating children, participation in community's activities, their role in household economy etc. The significant social impacts, increased awareness, confidence and living in a more dignified life itself and somehow the improvement in economic level are remarkable achievements in the field of poverty reduction and women empowerment.

Impact analysis of microfinance suggests that the majority of borrowers who already have some business skills and education are more likely to succeed. This study carried out an impact assessment follow-up survey and findings on the poverty effects of microfinance program. The finding of this study is microfinance continues to reduce poverty among poor borrowers and within the local economy. It raises income level, living standard of the clients.

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